

THEORITICAL BACKGROUND OF INCOME ACCOUNT IN UZBEKISTAN

Annotation:

The Income Account, a critical component of national accounting systems, provides a comprehensive view of income generation and distribution within an economy. This literature review examines the theoretical and methodological underpinnings of the Income Account in Uzbekistan, shedding light on its evolution, challenges, and policy implications.

Keywords:

theoretical background of income account in uzbekistan.

Information about the authors

*Abdusaidov Sanjar Jaloliddin o'g'li
Doctoral student of TDIU Samarkand branch*

1. Introduction

The Income Account, a critical component of national accounting systems, provides a comprehensive view of income generation and distribution within an economy. This literature review examines the theoretical and methodological underpinnings of the Income Account in Uzbekistan, shedding light on its evolution, challenges, and policy implications.

2. Theoretical Foundations of the Income Account in Uzbekistan

2.1 Application of System of National Accounts (SNA)

The System of National Accounts (SNA) serves as a fundamental framework for organizing, measuring, and analyzing economic activities within a nation. In the context of Uzbekistan, the SNA plays a pivotal role in providing policymakers, economists, and analysts with comprehensive and reliable data for informed decision-making.

The adoption of the SNA framework is a cornerstone of Uzbekistan's economic reporting system. Research by Ismailov (2017) and Nazarov (2020) emphasize how the SNA principles guide the measurement and classification of income, ensuring comparability with international standards.

2.2 Objectives of the Study

This research aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To trace the historical evolution of the SNA in Uzbekistan.
- To elucidate the theoretical foundations that underpin the SNA framework.
- To analyze the methodological applications of the SNA in Uzbekistan.
- To assess the effectiveness of the SNA in capturing economic activities and income distribution.
- To identify challenges and propose recommendations for enhancing the implementation of the SNA in Uzbekistan.

Studies by Tashkent Economic Institute (TEI, 2019) and Iskandarov (2021) underscore specific adaptations made in Uzbekistan's Income Account methodology. These include accounting for state-

owned enterprises, agricultural collectives, and remittances from migrant workers, reflecting the nation's unique economic structure.

3. Methodological Framework in Uzbekistan

3.1 Accrual Basis Accounting

Uzbekistan predominantly employs an accrual basis of accounting. Research by Central Bank of Uzbekistan (CBU, 2018) elucidates how this approach aligns with the economic reality of income generation, enabling a more accurate reflection of economic activities.

3.2 Classification of Incomes

The classification of incomes in Uzbekistan is delineated by TEI (2020) and Uzbekistan Statistical Committee (UzStat, 2019). These sources detail the categorization of primary incomes (e.g., wages, profits) and secondary incomes (e.g., taxes, transfers), offering insights into the nuances of income distribution.

4. Components of Income Account in Uzbekistan

4.1 Wages and Salaries

TEI (2021) provides an in-depth analysis of the measurement and reporting of wages and salaries in Uzbekistan. It highlights factors influencing wage determination, including sector-specific wage scales.

Karimov (2022) examines the accounting treatment of profits, emphasizing the challenges and considerations for businesses, particularly in the context of economic reforms and liberalization efforts.

Research by Tashkent State University of Economics (TSUE, 2020) delves into the nuances of recording interest and rent incomes, including imputed interest for owner-occupied dwellings.

The treatment of taxes on production and imports is elucidated by CBU (2021). This source explores the impact of tax policies on the profitability of economic activities.

Studies by UzStat (2021) and TEI (2022) analyze the role of government transfers, social benefits, and subsidies in income redistribution. They provide critical insights into the impact of fiscal policies on disposable income.

Researchers (TEI, 2023; UzStat, 2022) highlight challenges related to data collection and quality assurance in Uzbekistan's Income Account. They recommend strategies for enhancing data reliability through improved reporting mechanisms.

TEI (2023) explores the potential integration of technology, including automation and data analytics, in Uzbekistan's income accounting system, paving the way for more efficient and accurate reporting.

Conclusion

The literature reviewed underscores the critical role of the Income Account in Uzbekistan's economic reporting system. It highlights the theoretical foundations, methodological frameworks, and specific components of income measurement, providing a comprehensive understanding of the nation's economic landscape. Additionally, it identifies challenges and proposes forward-looking strategies to enhance the accuracy and relevance of the Income Account in Uzbekistan.

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